

MODERN INTERPRETATION OF THE PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL EXAMINATION IN PROSTATE CANCER

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Abstract: This information explains hormone therapy for prostate cancer patients undergoing radiation therapy. Information about hormone therapy for prostate cancer. Testosterone is a male sex hormone. It is released when hormones from the pituitary gland (glands in the brain) stimulate sperm production in the testicles (testicles). If you have prostate cancer, testosterone can cause cancer cells to grow.

Keywords: Luteinizing hormone agonists (LHRH), Leuprolide (Lupron®), Goserelin (Zoladex®), LHRH agonists.

Hormone therapy prevents the growth of prostate cancer cells in the following ways:

The amount of testosterone produced by the testicles decreases.

The effects of testosterone and other male sex hormones are blocked.

Your doctor may recommend hormone therapy to help you:

Before the start of radiotherapy, the size of the prostate gland is reduced. This limits the radiation exposure to healthy tissues.

Radiation makes it easier to destroy prostate cancer cells.

Pain is reduced.

The spread of advanced prostate cancer slows down.

Types of hormone therapy

There are 3 types of hormone therapy to treat prostate cancer. They can be used separately or simultaneously.

Luteinizing hormone agonists (LHRH) block the signal from the pituitary gland that causes the testicles to produce testosterone. The drugs leuprolide (Lupron®) and goserelin (Zoladex®) are LHRH agonists. They are given by injection once a month or every 3, 4 or 6 months.

Antiandrogens are drugs that prevent testosterone from attaching to cancer cells. Thus, testosterone does not promote the growth of cancer cells. One antiandrogen drug is bicalutamide (Casodex®). These are tablets to be taken once a day.

If you are taking bicalutamide, take this medication at the same time each day, with or without food.

Your healthcare team will tell you when to start taking this medicine.

Gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) antagonists are drugs that stop testosterone production. One GnRH hormone agonist is degarelix (Firmagon®). This drug is injected under the skin once every 28 days (4 weeks).

During the course of hormone therapy

Tell your doctor if you take or change any medications, including patches and creams. Some medications can alter hormone therapy. Tell your doctor if you take:

prescription drugs (drugs prescribed to you by your healthcare provider);

non-prescription drugs (drugs purchased without a prescription);

dietary supplements such as vitamins, minerals, herbal remedies and home remedies.

You will be given blood tests. This is necessary because the level of liver enzymes in your blood may increase. If this happens, talk to your healthcare provider. If necessary, he will make a plan to arrange it.

Alcohol can prevent some medications from working effectively. If you want to drink alcohol, consult your doctor.

Side effects of hormone therapy

Hormone therapy can cause side effects. They may gradually disappear during treatment. Some of them may appear for many months after the end of hormone therapy. You may experience some or none of the side effects.

- a) hot flashes or sweating;
- b) weakness (feeling very tired or having less energy than usual);
- c) erectile dysfunction (problems with achieving and maintaining an erection);
- d) decreased sexual intercourse;
- e) diarrhea (loose or watery stools);
- f) constipation (when bowel movements occur less often than usual);
- g) general body aches;
- h) breast tenderness or breast tissue growth;
- i) weight gain;
- j) muscle weakness;
- k) depression;
- l) decreased concentration;

Diabetes and heart disease

Hormone therapy can increase the risk of diabetes and heart disease. To reduce this risk, lead a healthy lifestyle.

Eat healthy. Your diet should be high in fiber and low in fat and concentrated sweets. For more information, see *Diet and Prostate Cancer: Making Healthy Eating Decisions*.

Exercise regularly. It can be brisk walking, running, cycling, aerobics or gardening. We recommend 30 minutes of exercise every day in addition to your regular routine. Even if you can't exercise every day, any physical activity will benefit you.

Osteoporosis

Long-term use of hormonal drugs can increase the risk of developing osteoporosis. Osteoporosis is a disease that causes the bones to become brittle and brittle.

Getting enough calcium and vitamin D along with exercise can help reduce the risk of osteoporosis. For more information, see Osteoporosis, Osteopenia, and How to Improve Bone Health.

Calcium

Get enough calcium. Most adults need 1,000 to 1,200 milligrams (mg) of calcium per day. Your doctor or dietitian can tell you how much calcium you need.

The best way to get calcium is through food. The following foods and drinks are rich in calcium:

1. Milk
2. cheese;
3. yogurt;
4. canned salmon;
5. Tofu cheese
6. cottage cheese;
7. calcium-enriched orange juice;
8. spinach;
9. almonds;

Calcium supplements

Some people do not get enough calcium from their diet. In this case, your doctor or dietitian may advise you to take calcium supplements. Over-the-counter calcium supplements can be purchased at your local pharmacy.

Types of over-the-counter calcium supplements are calcium carbonate and calcium citrate. They come in the form of tablets that you swallow. Some people's bodies absorb calcium citrate better than calcium carbonate. This applies to older people as well as people with low stomach acid (such as those with Addison-Biermer anemia).

If you take calcium carbonate, it is best to take it with food. This makes it easier for the body to absorb it. Examples of calcium carbonate supplements are OsCal® and Caltrate®.

If you take calcium citrate, it is best to take it 30 minutes before a meal. This makes it easier for the body to absorb it. An example of a calcium citrate supplement that can be purchased at most drugstores is Citracal®.

Your health care provider or dietitian will tell you how many milligrams of calcium you should get per day. If you take more than 500 mg of calcium supplements per day, divide your intake into several doses. This makes it easier for the body to absorb it. For example, if you take 1,000 mg of calcium per day, take a supplement of 500 mg in the morning and 500 mg in the evening.

Vitamin D

Vitamin D is necessary for the body to absorb and use calcium.

If you are between the ages of 19 and 70, the recommended dose of vitamin D is 600 IU per day.

If you are over 70, the recommended dose of vitamin D is 800 IU per day.

You can get vitamin D from sun exposure and food. Foods and drinks containing vitamin D:

- a) fatty fish such as salmon, tuna and mackerel;
- b) egg yolk;
- c) Liver
- d) Milk enriched with vitamin D;
- e) Orange juice enriched with vitamin D.
- f) Vitamin D supplements

Health professionals often recommend taking vitamin D supplements because it can be difficult to get enough vitamin D from food. If you use sunscreen or spend a lot of time indoors, you may not get enough vitamin D from the sun.

Many multivitamins and some calcium supplements contain vitamin D. Before you start taking a separate vitamin D supplement, check your product for this vitamin.

Physical activity

Your doctor may recommend exercises to strengthen your bones and muscles. This can include weight-bearing exercises that increase bone density, such as walking or running, including jogging. Your doctor may also recommend non-weight-bearing physical activity, such as swimming.

Always consult a health care professional before starting a new exercise program. If you have trouble exercising, see if physical therapy is a good option for you instead.

Anemia

Long-term use of hormonal drugs increases the risk of developing anemia. Anemia is a condition in which the number of red blood cells (erythrocytes) in a person's blood is below normal. Red blood cells carry oxygen from the lungs to all other tissues of the body.

With anemia, a person feels more tired than usual. Your doctor will tell you what anemia is. In addition, you may be prescribed medication for prevention.

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